

ARCHITECTURE

CREATION OF INNOVATION WITH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE FIRST TIME IN THE CONDITIONS OF NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC

Gunel Seyidzadeh

a.e.f.d.,Dose

Nakhchivan Scientific-Research Institute of Agriculture named after academician Hasan Aliyev, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

SCHAFFUNG VON INNOVATIONEN DURCH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIEN – ERSTMALS UNTER DEN BEDINGUNGEN DER AUTONOMEN REPUBLIK NACHITSCHEWAN

Gunel Seyidzadeh

a.e.f.d.,Dose

Nachitschewan Wissenschaftliches Forschungsinstitut für Landwirtschaft, benannt nach dem Akademiker Hasan Aliyev, Nachitschewan, Aserbajdschan

Abstract

One of the priority directions of agriculture is the intensive development of horticulture and fruit growing. At this stage of development, the production of healthy, certified and genetically stable planting material is of great importance for the establishment of gardens with high productivity and longevity. Especially in intensive horticultural systems, the organization of the field of horticulture on a scientific basis plays a strategically important role in increasing productivity indicators and ensuring the sustainability of production. Innovative ways applied to each sector in the development of the agricultural sector stimulate more intensive and rapid development by increasing productivity and quality.

In this context, on 05.12.2025, for the first time in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, with the application of innovative technologies, cultivation fields and a collection orchard were established in the city of Nakhchivan and Sharur Base of the Nakhchivan Scientific-Research Institute of Agriculture named after Academician Hasan Aliyev.

The main purpose of the study is to create a collection garden consisting of fruit varieties that can be adapted to the climatic conditions of the region in order to develop horticulture in the conditions of the autonomous republic. For this purpose, it is the development of intensive horticulture in accordance with the principles of market relations, the determination of priority directions and the study of efficiency with scientific foundations.

Zusammenfassung

Eine der Prioritäten der Landwirtschaft ist die intensive Entwicklung des Gartenbaus und des Obstanbaus. In dieser Entwicklungsphase ist die Produktion von gesundem, zertifiziertem und genetisch stabilem Pflanzgut von großer Bedeutung für die Anlage ertragreicher und langlebiger Gärten. Insbesondere in intensiven Gartenbausystemen spielt die wissenschaftliche Organisation der Anbauflächen eine strategisch wichtige Rolle für die Steigerung der Produktivität und die Sicherung der Nachhaltigkeit der Produktion. Innovative Ansätze in den einzelnen Sektoren der Landwirtschaft fördern eine intensivere und schnellere Entwicklung durch Steigerung von Produktivität und Qualität.

In diesem Zusammenhang wurden am 5. Dezember 2025 in der Autonomen Republik Nachitschewan erstmals Anbauflächen und eine Obstgartenanlage unter Anwendung innovativer Technologien in der Stadt Nachitschewan und auf dem Scharur-Gelände des nach Akademiemitglied Hasan Alijew benannten Wissenschaftlichen Forschungsinstituts für Landwirtschaft in Nachitschewan angelegt.

Hauptziel der Studie ist die Anlage eines Sammelgartens mit Obstsorten, die an die klimatischen Bedingungen der Region angepasst sind, um den Gartenbau in der autonomen Republik zu fördern. Dazu soll ein intensiver Gartenbau nach marktwirtschaftlichen Prinzipien entwickelt, Prioritäten gesetzt und die Effizienz wissenschaftlich fundiert untersucht werden.

Keywords: Innovative technologies, agriculture, agricultural sector, fruit growing, climate.

Schlüsselwörter: Innovative Technologien, Landwirtschaft, Agrarsektor, Obstanbau, Klima.

The modernization of agriculture and the efficient use of the agricultural potential of the regions are among the main directions of modern economic development strategies. The Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is distinguished by its specific geographical position and continental climate characteristics. The high solar radiation in the region, the length of the vegetation

period, and soil diversity create favorable opportunities for the development of fruit growing. However, the scarcity of precipitation and the limitation of water resources require the application of intensive and scientifically based nursery systems. A high-intensity cultivation system is an agricultural production model based

on the principles of dense plant placement and optimal use of soil, water, nutrients, light, and labor resources.

Innovative technology development in the agricultural sector serves as the main driving force of structural changes in world economies. Technology has also significantly affected the green industry, strengthening the development, production, and marketing of nursery plants. Intensive nursery production is a system aimed at the production of high-quality, certified planting material, which forms the basis of modern horticulture. When this system is integrated with innovative technologies, it leads to the structural transformation of the agricultural sector. [2, s. 2-3]

Intensive nursery production involves the production of genetically pure, disease-free, and high-yield potential planting material in a short period. This system includes the organization of certified mother orchards, optimization of vegetative propagation methods, use of modern substrate and container technologies, drip irrigation and fertigation systems, and phytosanitary monitoring and laboratory diagnostics. [6, s. 14-26].

Under the conditions of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the application of an intensive nursery system serves to ensure stable production by minimizing the region's climatic risks. For this reason, the limited availability of water resources makes the implementation of water-saving technologies a priority direction. Drip irrigation systems ensure the direct delivery of water to the root zone and minimize evaporation losses [3, pp. 6–7]. Through the fertigation method, the precise application of nutrients creates conditions for balanced plant nutrition. Thus, this approach reduces water consumption by 30–50%, minimizes mineral fertilizer losses, and at the same time contributes to the preservation of soil structure [7, pp. 191–198].

It has been established that the application of innovative technologies has a significant impact on increasing productivity, producing genetically healthy planting material, and enhancing the competitiveness of the agrarian sector in the region. In our republic, special attention is paid to the development of fruit growing. While the productivity of old-type orchards does not exceed 70–80 centners per hectare, the productivity of orchards established using innovative technologies in accordance with modern agrotechnical requirements reaches 300–400 c/ha [4, pp. 4–5]. For this reason, the

development of fruit growing in the region, especially the industrial-scale cultivation of species such as apple, pear, apricot, peach, cherry, and walnut, necessitates the organization of high-quality and certified nursery production. The application of innovative technologies not only increases the efficiency of intensive nursery farms but also creates a basis for ensuring phytosanitary safety and producing export-oriented products.

The main determinant of structural and functional changes in the nursery sector is technological innovation, which in modern production systems is aimed not only at increasing quantitative indicators but also at optimizing quality parameters, ensuring efficient use of resources, and maintaining ecological sustainability [5, pp 7-8.].

Research object and subject. The establishment of intensive-type nursery areas under the soil and climatic conditions of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Research purpose and objectives. The main purpose of the research is to establish nurseries consisting of fruit varieties adaptable to the climatic conditions of the region for the development of horticulture under the conditions of the autonomous republic. In the research object, studies are conducted on intensive nursery production (based on new varieties) through the application of innovative technologies. In this regard, the following tasks are carried out in the research:

- Increasing the development and efficiency of intensive horticulture in accordance with the principles of market relations;
- Studying fruit growing and nursery production on scientific bases through the application of innovative technologies;
- Comparing the regional development characteristics of nursery farms and determining priority directions.

Research method. In the research process, the establishment of modern nursery production under the soil and climatic conditions of the region, the introduction of adaptable varieties, and the study of their comparative characteristics are carried out

Experimental Part: Soil analyses of the research object were analyzed in the general analytical analysis laboratory of the Research Institute of Fruit-Growing and Tea-Growing of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Azerbaijan (Table 1).

Table 1

General soil analysis of the research object

Soil layer, cm	Name of indicator	Unit of measurement	Analysis result	Evaluation	Norm	Reference method
0-30	Nitrogen	%	0.11	medium	0.09-0.17	Kjeldahl
	Phosphorus	mg/kg	18	low	24-48	Olsen
	Lime	%	18.6	very limy	5-15	Scheibler Calcimeter
	Humus	%	1.9	low	2-3	Walkley Black
	pH	%	8.2	weak alkaline	6.6-7.5	Saturation pH meter
	Mechanical composition	%	40, 20, 40	sand, clay, silt		Hydrometric method
	Electrical conductivity	m/siemens	317	non-saline	0-2000	EC
30-60	Nitrogen	%	0.10	medium	0.09-0.17	Kjeldahl
	Phosphorus	mg/kg	9	very low	24-48	Olsen
	Lime	%	18.3	very limy	5-15	Scheibler Calcimeter
	Humus	%	1.5	low	2-3	Walkley Black
	pH	%	8.1	weak alkaline	6.6-7.5	Saturation pH meter
	Mechanical composition	%	38, 16, 46	sand, clay, silt		Hydrometric method
	Electrical conductivity	m/siemens	320	non-saline	0-2000	EC

The results of the conducted agrochemical analyses have shown that the selected areas are suitable for the establishment of intensive nursery and fruit-growing farms in terms of the soil's mechanical composition, level of provision with nutrients, water-physical properties, and climatic indicators. At the same time, the adaptation potential of the introduced varieties, their vegetative development indicators, and initial phenological observations provide a basis for achieving high results through their adaptation to the soil-climatic conditions of the region.

For the first time in the Autonomous Republic, nursery areas have been established through the application of innovative technologies (on 05.12.2025 at the

Nakhchivan city and Sharur Support Station of the Nakhchivan Agricultural Scientific Research Institute named after Academician Hasan Aliyev). Planting materials were obtained within the framework of cooperation from the Fruit Growing and Tea Growing Scientific Research Institute of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

In the newly established 1 ha nursery areas, 50 thousand rootstocks of foreign origin, including VSL 2, Gizella 6, Garnem 15, Adara, and Myrobolan 29-C varieties, have been planted. The nursery has been provided with an irrigation system in accordance with innovative technologies (Table 2), (Figure 1)

Table 2

Characteristics of the Studied Varieties

Variety Name	Origin	Field of use	Soil Compatibility	Yielding	Climate Resistance	Planting Scheme	Number
VSL 2	Lannesiana cherry x steppe cherry	Sweet cherry, sour cherry	Heavy moist, clayey Soils	Yields in the 3rd year	Resistant to cold, heat, drought	5x2.5m	1800 units
Gizella 6	Prunus cerasus x Prunus canescens	Sweet cherry, sour cherry	Deep and irrigated soils	Yield early	Resistant to winter, cold	3x1m	10000 Units
Garnem 15	Prunus dulcis x Prunus persica	Peach, nectarine, almond, apricot	Heavy clayey, and limy soils	Yields in the 2nd-3rd year	Resistant to cold, heat, drought	5x3.5m	8000 Units
Adara	Prunus cerasifera x Prunus dulcis	Sweet cherry, peach, sour cherry	Clayey, well-drained soils	Early and abundant yield	Cold resistant	4.5x2.5m	3,500 Units
Myrobolan 29-C	Prunus cerasifera	Plum, apricot, cherry plum	Heavy clayey, high and medium drained soils	Yields early and abundantly	Moderately drought resistance	5x4m	10500 Units

Figure 1. Newly established nursery

Conclusion

It should be noted that the creation of opportunities for the correct and efficient use of sustainable development resources in important areas of agriculture using innovative technologies is of great importance.

Conducted research shows that the application of innovative technologies for intensive nursery production in the conditions of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is efficient from agro-ecological and economic points of view. The nursery established on December 5, 2025, is an important platform for scientifically based intensive gardening and the production of healthy planting material in the region.

References

1. Abobatta, W. F. Intensive fruit orchards cultivation. *J Plant Sci Phytopathol.*, 5, 072–075., (2021). DOI:10.29328/journal.jpsp.1001064 — overview of high-intensity orchard cultivation systems. <https://www.plantsciencejournal.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/jpsp-aid1064>
2. C.R. Hall., “Impacts of technology on the development, production, and marketing of nursery crops”., 9, 2-3. *International Society for Horticultural Science*, (2020).
3. Gheorghe.S, Alexandru. L, “New technologies and technical equipment for fruit farms”., 10, 6-7. *National Institute for Research-Development of Machines and Installations designed for Agriculture and Food Industry.* (2023)
4. Cəfərov, Y., İbrahimov, C., Xəlilov, E., Cabbarov, S., Hüseynov, K., İbrahimov, C., (2020). *Tumlu və çəyirdəkli meyvə bağlarında inteqrirlənmiş mübarizə tədbirləri.*, 52 , 4-5. *Aqrar Xidmətlər Agentliyi Bitki Mühafizə və Texniki Bitkilər Elmi-Tədqiqat İnstitutu.*
5. *Brazilian Journal of Fruit Growing.*, “The role of research and technology in shaping a sustainable fruit industry: European advances and prospects”., 26., 7-8., (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-29452006000300049>
6. CARVALHO, A.J.C.; FONTES, P.S.F.; FREITAS, M.S.M.; MONNERAT, P.H.; FONTES, A.G. Yellow passion fruit plant nutritional diagnosis at different phenological stages by the Diagnosis and Recommendation Integrated System Method. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, New York, v.34, n.4, p.14-26, (2011).
7. ARROBAS, M.; FERREIRA, I.Q.; FREITAS, S.; VERDIAL, J.; RODRIGUES, M.Á. Guidelines for fertilizer use in vineyards based on nutrient content of grapevine parts. *Scientia Horticulturae*, Amsterdam, v.172, p.191-198, (2014).